

MENTAL HEALTH AND COMMUNITY WELLBEING

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Abstract

The interplay between mental health and community wellbeing is crucial for fostering a health society. Mental health encompasses emotional, psychological, and social dimensions, significantly influencing individual's quality of life. Community wellbeing, on the other hand, reflects the collection health and quality of life of a community's members. Recent research emphasizes the importance of creating "wellbeing responsive communities" which focus on intentional mental health promotion through local empowerment, co-creation, and contextualized solutions. These communities recognize the interdependence between individual and collective well-being, advocating for a holistic approach that addresses both mental health symptoms and overall wellness.

Introduction

Humans require mental health and well-being just as much as oxygen to survive. It is critical to understand that mental health should be a top concern in order to live a happy and peaceful lifestyle. The importance of mental health and well-being has been recognized in spiritual countries such as India, where saints (also known as sadhus or gurus) used to meditate and do yoga to maintain their mental health. In recent years, all companies have implemented programs to educate employees on the importance of mental health and well-being, but consultation about mental health issues is still considered a social stigma, causing people to avoid discussing their mental health and

seeking treatment for any mental health issues. However, we must recognize that having mental health issues is normal and should be treated. Let us strive to learn more about the value of mental health and well-being.

What is Mental Health?

The “**World Health Organization (WHO)** defines mental health as a condition of well-being in which an individual recognizes their strengths, copes with everyday stressors, works successfully and fruitfully, and can contribute to society and community.” Mental health refers to an individual's emotional, psychological, and social well-being. It influences how people think, feel, and act in a certain scenario. It also influences how one manages stress and makes healthy decisions.

Mental health is crucial at all stages of life, whether in childhood, adolescence, or maturity. It plays a significant part in many aspects of life, and it is critical to protect and develop psychological wellness through suitable measures.

What is Mental Illness?

In “**The Mental Health Care Act, 2017** section 2(s) defined the "mental illness" as a substantial disorder of thinking, mood, perception, orientation or memory that grossly impairs judgment, behaviour, capacity to recognise reality or ability to meet the ordinary demands of life, mental conditions associated with the abuse of alcohol and drugs, but does not include mental retardation which is a condition of arrested or incomplete development of mind of a person, specially characterised by sub normality of intelligence.”

A person's mood, thoughts, and behaviour can all be impacted by a variety of mental health issues together referred to as mental illnesses. Anxiety disorders, eating disorders, schizophrenia, depression, and addictive behaviours are a few examples of mental disease or mental health issues.

To put it simply, mental illness arises when the brain malfunctions, just like any other organ like the kidney or the heart. It is impossible to maintain control of one's thoughts or point of view when suffering from mental health issues.

Mental Health vs Mental Illness

Despite the frequent confusion between the phrases, mental health and mental illness are not synonymous. While mental illness is a diagnosed ailment that impacts an individual's thoughts and behaviour, mental health refers to an individual's state of mental, emotional, and social well-being. Not everyone suffers from a mental disease, and even those who do can experience good mental health at times. However, everyone can experience moments or periods of bad mental health. It is crucial to understand that poor mental health is not necessarily the result of mental disease and that mental illness does not always cause poor mental health. Whether or not a mental disease is present, life events or any other external variables can have an impact on an individual's mental health.

Community wellbeing

Feature	Definition
Community	A group of people who are brought together around a shared purpose. It may include a support team, school, programme, government department, network, or region.
Responsive	The community has an awareness of the needs and context of individual and collective community members and has the language, knowledge, methods, and skills to work side-by-side

	together and intentionally respond to these needs in a contextualized or personalized manner.
Wellbeing	<p>A mental health and wellbeing outcome which is operationalized in the language of the community and reflects the interdependence</p> <p>between (i) mental health and wellbeing (dual continua) and (ii) individual and community wellbeing.</p>
Growth needs	The wellbeing, trauma, developmental, therapeutic, medical, economic, social-cultural, and life needs of individual and collective community members.
Connected thriving local community	<p>A community where human connections and shared solutions are evident;</p> <p>individual and collective growth needs are met; and meaning, aspiration and satisfaction are expressed at the individual and collective levels.</p>

Types of Mental Health

Mental health encompasses a wide range of disorders that affect an individual's emotional, psychological, and social well-being. The types of mental health disorders prevalent in India can be categorized as follows:

- **Depressive Disorders:** Depression is one of the most common mental health issues, characterized by persistent sadness, hopelessness, and a loss of interest in activities once enjoyed. Symptoms can include fatigue, changes in appetite, sleep disturbances, and difficulty concentrating. It significantly impairs daily functioning and can lead to severe consequences, including suicide if untreated. In India, depressive disorders affect millions, contributing to a substantial portion of the disease burden.
- **Anxiety Disorders:** Anxiety disorders involve excessive and persistent worry or fear that disrupts daily life. This category includes several conditions, such as generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, social anxiety disorder, and obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD). Individuals may experience physical symptoms like heart palpitations and shortness of breath, along with emotional distress. The prevalence of anxiety disorders in India is notably high, exacerbated by factors such as stress from urbanization and the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.
- **Bipolar Disorder:** Bipolar disorder is marked by extreme mood swings, including episodes of mania (elevated mood) and depression. During manic phases, individuals may exhibit increased energy, impulsive behavior, and an inflated sense of self-importance. The depressive episodes can lead to significant impairment in functioning. This disorder poses challenges in diagnosis and management, particularly among the youth in India.
- **Schizophrenia:** Schizophrenia is a severe mental disorder characterized by distorted thinking, perceptions, emotions, language, and sense of self. Symptoms may include hallucinations, delusions, and disorganized thinking. Schizophrenia often emerges in late adolescence or early adulthood, making its impact particularly significant during critical developmental years.
- **Substance Use Disorders:** Substance use disorders involve the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. These disorders

can lead to significant health, social, and economic issues. In India, the prevalence of substance use disorders is rising, often linked to societal stressors and inadequate mental health support systems.

- **Common Mental Disorders (CMDs):** Common mental disorders include a range of neurotic and nonpsychotic conditions, primarily focusing on depression and anxiety. The National Mental Health Survey of India indicated that CMDs have a high prevalence, particularly among women and urban populations. These disorders often go unrecognized and untreated, leading to substantial disability and economic burden.
- **Neurodevelopmental Disorders:** These disorders, which include conditions like Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and autism spectrum disorders, typically manifest in childhood and can affect functioning throughout life. Early diagnosis and intervention are crucial for improving outcomes for individuals with neurodevelopmental disorders.

	Males	Females	
Both sexes			14.4% (13.1–
All mental disorders	14.3% (12.9–15.7)	14.2% (12.8–15.6)	15.8)
Depressive disorders	3.3% (3.1–3.6)	2.7% (2.5–3.0)	3.9% (3.6–4.3)

Anxiety disorders	3.3% (3.0–3.5)	2.7% (2.4–2.9)	3.9% (3.6–4.3)
Conduct disorder	0.8% (0.6–1.0)	1.0% (0.8–1.3)	0.6% (0.4–0.7)
Bipolar disorder	0.6% (0.5–0.7)	0.6% (0.5–0.7)	0.6% (0.5–0.7)
Schizophrenia	0.3% (0.2–0.3)	0.3% (0.2–0.3)	0.2% (0.2–0.3)
Other mental disorders	1.8% (1.5–2.0)	2.1% (1.8–2.4)	1.4% (1.2–1.7)

Mental health is a critical aspect of overall well-being, influencing how individuals think, feel, and act. It encompasses emotional, psychological, and social aspects, affecting how people handle stress, relate to others, and make choices. Despite this high prevalence,

many individuals remain unaware of their conditions or hesitate to seek help. Several factors contribute to mental health, which can be categorized into biological,

psychological, and social influences. Biological factors include genetics, brain chemistry, and physical health conditions, all of which can predispose individuals to mental disorders. Psychological factors encompass beliefs, coping mechanisms, and experiences of trauma, which can significantly impact mental well-being. Social factors such as relationships, financial stability, and cultural influences also play a crucial role in shaping mental health. Understanding these factors is essential for effective mental health promotion and intervention. By addressing the underlying causes and improving access to mental health resources, society can work towards reducing the stigma associated with mental illness and encouraging individuals to seek the help they need.

Community interventions

Over the years, prevention research has emphasized that working in isolation with individuals, families, or schools is insufficient to achieve meaningful reductions in unfavorable mental health outcomes, such as substance use, at the population level. This has resulted in the widespread adoption of community-based preventative methods that focus not only on lowering problem behaviours but also on improving community well-being and ownership.

The Icelandic Prevention Model (IPM) is one of the most successful approaches for reducing substance use among teenagers. This methodology works within a community, focusing on the underlying environmental and social variables that contribute to substance use. These factors include a lack of consequences and supervision in the social environment (from parents and other adults), a lack of personal and communal commitment to traditional, positive values (including lofty educational goals), and a scarcity of opportunities for constructive and prosaically growth (such as organized recreational and extracurricular activities like sports, music, drama, and after-school clubs).

The major goal of this method is to mobilize society against problematic substance use, with a focus on community involvement and cooperation to facilitate long-term incremental changes in the environmental and social landscapes.

The strategy has been successfully applied in rural communities and across a variety of geographical locations, including in low- and middle-income nations such as Chile.

Laws Related to Mental Health

The Mentally unhealthy persons deserve legal protection. It is undeniable that concern for them has been translated in International Conventions and Municipal Legislations. Though it is difficult to trace legislative history but legal protection to mentally unhealthy persons in modern sense began with the dawn of twentieth century. The civil protection has been extended, earlier by the Indian Lunacy Act, 1912 and presently by the Mental Health Act, 2017. There is a need to emphasize the importance of protecting mentally ill persons. There is a dynamic relationship between the concept of mental illness, the treatment and the law. Legislation has played an important role in protecting and promoting the rights and interests of persons with mental illness.

PROVISIONS UNDER THE CONSTITUTION OF INDIA, 1950

The preamble of the Constitution of the India, 1950 assures the equal treatment and equality of opportunity and status to all citizens. No discrimination is allowed. There are certain provisions in the Constitution which are concerned with mental health of a person.

Notwithstanding the fact that the Constitution of India implies in principle that the mentally ill citizens are well within their right to enjoy the same rights and privileges as are guaranteed to other citizens. It is necessary for legislatures to make laws for mentally ill sections of the society which suitably give effect to the rights and privileges of such persons.

The weaker sections of the society deserves special or preferential treatment. Basically, the social approach to the problem is deficient. It has been left for legislation to identify the mentally ill. The legislative power of the state under Entry 6 List-II of Seventh Schedule of the Constitution deals with public health and sanitation; hospitals and dispensaries and Entry 16 List-III of Seventh Schedule of the Constitution deals with lunacy and mental deficiency which includes places for the reception or treatment of lunatics and mentally ill people. The fundamental right to life and liberty which has been widely interpreted by the Supreme Court of India in a number of cases includes the right to live with human dignity and right to health. The maintenance and improvement of public health is one of the obligations that flow from Article 21 of the Constitution. This means that mentally ill have fundamental right to receive mental health care and humane living conditions in the mental hospitals.

In *Veena Sethi V state of Bihar (1982)*, the court was informed through a letter that some prisoners who had been '*insane*' at the time of trial but had subsequently been declared 'sane', had not been released due to inaction of the state authorities and had remained in jail for 20 to 30 years. The court directed them to be released forthwith, considering the requirements of protection of right to life and liberty of the citizen against the lawlessness of the state.

In *Dr. Upendra Baxi v State of Uttar Pradesh (1983)* the Supreme Court called upon to enforce the human rights of the occupants of state protective Homes for Women. The court ordered that a panel to examine the inmates of Agra home and submit the report. The report showed that 33 out of 50 inmates had varying degrees of mental disability and had not been examined at time of admission to the home. Despite this the superintendent had released 14 of them without determining their mental state and with no money to cover even their train fare to their home towns. ***The court recommended that psychiatric treatment be provided to the mentally ill inmates, for which the record of the time and place of the treatment should be maintained.***

In ***Rakesh Chandra Narayan v State of Bihar, (1989)*** certain cardinal principles were laid down by the apex court that the “*Right of a mentally ill person to food, water, personal hygiene, sanitation and recreation is an extension of the right of life as in Article 21 of the constitution. Quality norms and standards to mental health are non-negotiable. Treatment, teaching, training and research must be integrated to produce the desired results.*”

In ***S.P. Sathe v State of Maharashtra (Writ Petition No. 1537, 1984)***, The Bombay High Court regulated the ***prescription of indiscriminate electric shocks to mentally ill persons***. The court also directed that reports should be made whenever electric shocks were given by prison psychiatrist. Article 47 of the Constitution of India, 1950 imposes duty upon the state to raise the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and the improvement of public health which includes all components of health including mental health. Thus, there are enough constitutional provisions and judicial holdings which conserve, protect and promote the welfare of mentally ill persons. But now electronic shock as known as ECT has been banned as in ***The Mental Health Care Act 2017, section 95*** clarifies that the person who is suffering from mental illness shall not be provided that following treatment-

- (a) Electroconvulsive therapy without the use of muscle relaxants and anaesthesia.
- (b) Electroconvulsive therapy for minors,
- (c) Sterilization of men or women, when sterilization is intended as a treatment of mental illness,
- (d) Chained in any manner or form whatsoever.

If the psychiatrist in charge has said that Electroconvulsive therapy to be done on the minor than consent of the guardian of is required.

Mental Health Problems Statistics Worldwide

According to a study conducted in 2018, by Our World in Data,

- Anxiety affects around 284 million people in the world
- Depression affects nearly 264 million people
- Alcohol use disorder affects 107 million people in the world
- Drug use disorder affects 71 million people across the world
- Schizophrenia affects 20 million people
- Bipolar disorder affects 46 million people
- Eating disorders affect 16 million people

Even though the figures above relate to disorders that have been officially recognized, some people continue to keep their mental health problems hidden. Any indication, no matter how slight, of a mental health issue must be taken seriously since it may eventually result in psychological disorder. The number of mental health issues in the world has been rising annually, and the Covid19 pandemic has caused a sharp increase in these issues. People were terrified during COVID, and this planted the seed of mental illness in the minds of those who lost loved ones. After COVID, the number of cases of anxiety, depression, and other personality disorders has increased.

Signs of Mental Health Problems

Mental health issues can manifest in various ways, and recognizing the signs is crucial for early intervention and support. Individuals experiencing mental health challenges often exhibit emotional changes that can be persistent and intense. Common signs include persistent feelings of sadness, hopelessness, or worthlessness, which can dominate a person's emotional landscape, leading to a pervasive sense of despair. Frequent mood swings or emotional outbursts may also occur, indicating underlying mental health challenges. Additionally, excessive fears, worries, or feelings of guilt can overwhelm an individual, interfering with daily life. A noticeable disinterest in activities once enjoyed can signal depression or other mental health disorders.

Behavioural changes are often among the most observable signs of mental health issues. These may include withdrawal from friends, family, and social activities, as individuals may isolate themselves, pulling away from social interactions and support networks. Significant changes in sleeping or eating patterns can also be indicative, manifesting as insomnia, excessive sleeping, loss of appetite, or overeating. A decline in self-care, such as neglecting personal hygiene and grooming, can be a red flag that the individual is struggling. Furthermore, engaging in reckless or impulsive behaviours,

including substance abuse or other forms of self-destructive actions, can signal a deeper issue.

Cognitive changes can significantly impact an individual's ability to function effectively. Signs in this category include difficulty concentrating, thinking clearly, or making decisions, which can manifest as forgetfulness or a general sense of confusion. Confused thinking or a reduced ability to concentrate may make it challenging to focus on tasks or follow conversations. In severe cases, individuals may experience delusions, paranoia, or hallucinations, leading to distorted perceptions of reality that require immediate attention.

Physical symptoms can also be indicative of mental health issues, often presenting as unexplained ailments. Persistent physical symptoms, such as headaches, digestive problems, or chronic pain, may not respond to standard medical treatment and can be linked to mental health conditions. Unexplained aches and pains, along with fluctuations in libido, can reflect underlying emotional or psychological issues.

One of the most serious indicators of mental health distress is the presence of suicidal thoughts or behaviours. Key signs include thoughts about death or suicide, where expressions of wanting to die or feeling that life are not worth living should be taken seriously. Conversations about wanting to hurt oneself or end one's life should prompt immediate action and support. Engaging in selfharm or suicidal behaviours, including any actions taken to intentionally harm oneself, requires urgent intervention. Recognizing these signs is essential for providing support and seeking professional help. If you or someone you know is experiencing several of these symptoms, particularly suicidal thoughts, it is crucial to reach out to a mental health professional or crisis hotline for immediate assistance.

Tips for Good Mental Health and Wellbeing

Maintaining good mental health and wellbeing is essential for leading a fulfilling life. Here are several effective strategies to enhance mental wellbeing: One of the foundational tips for good mental health is “reframing unhelpful thoughts” Our thoughts significantly influence our feelings and behaviours. Recognizing and challenging negative thought patterns can lead to a more positive mindset. Techniques such as cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) can help individuals learn to think differently about their situations, reducing feelings of anxiety and depression.

“**Mindfulness and being present**” are also crucial for mental wellbeing. Taking time to focus on the present moment can help individuals gain perspective and reduce stress. Mindfulness practices, such as meditation and mindful breathing, encourage awareness of thoughts and feelings without judgment, fostering a sense of calm and clarity. “Quality sleep” plays a vital role in mental health. Good sleep hygiene, including maintaining a regular sleep schedule and creating a restful environment, can significantly improve mood and cognitive function. Sleep deprivation can lead to irritability and increased stress, making it essential to prioritize restorative sleep.

“**Social connections**” are fundamental to mental health. Spending quality time with friends and family, whether in person or through virtual means, can combat feelings of loneliness and isolation. Engaging in conversations about feelings and experiences can provide support and strengthen relationships, which are crucial during challenging times. Adopting a “healthy lifestyle” is another key aspect of mental wellbeing. Regular physical activity, a balanced diet, and avoiding harmful substances like excessive alcohol and nicotine can improve mood and overall health. Exercise, in particular, has been shown to reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression by releasing endorphins and improving self-esteem.

Engaging in “**activities that bring joy**” is essential for mental health. Whether it’s pursuing a hobby, learning a new skill, or simply taking time to relax, doing things that

make you happy can enhance your sense of fulfilment and purpose. Setting aside time for personal enjoyment can help recharge mental energy and improve emotional resilience. Lastly, “practicing gratitude” can shift focus from negative thoughts to positive experiences. Keeping a gratitude journal or regularly reflecting on what you appreciate in life can foster a more optimistic outlook. This practice helps individuals recognize the good amidst challenges, contributing to overall mental wellbeing. By implementing these strategies, individuals can cultivate a healthier mental state, enhance their resilience, and improve their overall quality of life. Regularly investing in mental health is as important as physical health, and making small, consistent changes can lead to significant improvements over time.

Conclusion

This study extends current understanding of the connections between social capital and mental health. Individuals reporting a higher sense of community in their neighbourhoods experienced reduced symptoms of depression, anxiety and stress. These findings highlight the importance of social relationships and community connectedness for mental well-being. Fostering a positive sense of community can serve as a buffer against mental health challenges. Strategies to support improved sense of community and build social capital may benefit mental health equity. Incorporating information on social factors like community belonging can strengthen the capacity of health surveys to link social determinants to mental health outcomes.

At the community level, creating environments that promote social inclusion and reduce isolation may have positive impacts on mental well-being. Addressing social determinants of health, such as poverty, discrimination and adverse life events, is crucial for supporting mental health. Prioritizing mental health promotion and prevention at the community level, in addition to treatment, can yield significant benefits. Empowering individuals with proactive well-being strategies, while also addressing systemic factors, is a comprehensive approach to enhancing mental health and community thriving. This

research underscores the vital role of social connections, community belonging, and addressing social determinants for supporting positive mental health outcomes. Integrating these insights into mental health research, policy and practice can lead to improved well-being at both the individual and community levels.

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